

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

Project 'CarboSeq'

Deliverable WP3.1-3.5

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

Due date of deliverable: M46

Actual submission date: 01.04.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Project title: CarboSeq

Project website: <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq>

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	WP3.1-3.5
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE:	WP3
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Biochar and other organic amendments
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	Agroscope, Switzerland
AUTHOR:	Jens Leifeld, Briec Hardy, Alice Budai, Lars Elsgaard, Sonja G. Keel, Florent Levavasseur, Zhi Liang, Claudio Mondini, César Plaza, Leonor Rodrigues.
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14046237
LICENSE	CC BY 4.0
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	CO/PU

CarboSeq

Soil organic carbon sequestration potential of agricultural soils in Europe

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

Reported Deliverables: D3.1 – D3.5

Authors: Jens Leifeld, Briec Hardy, Alice Budai, Lars Elsgaard, Sonja G. Keel, Florent Levavasasseur, Zhi Liang, Claudio Mondini, César Plaza, Leonor Rodrigues.

Content

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Biochar stability and modeling	8
2.1. Biochar feedstock quality, pyrolysis yield and biochar stability	8
2.2. Modelling of biochar in RothC	14
2.3. Biochar classification and C emission factors	16
2.4. Biochar applied in Europe.....	16
2.5. Effects of abiotic and biotic drivers for biochar stability.....	17
3. Methodology to calibrate and validate C inputs and stability from other organic amendments	19
3.1. Modelling of other organic amendments in RothC.....	19
3.1.1 Material & Methods	23
3.1.2.1 Roth C model versions	23
3.1.2.2 Laboratory incubation database	23
3.1.2.3 Long term field experiment database.....	23
3.1.2.3 Simulation of lab mineralization data	24
3.1.2.4 Simulation of Long-term experiments (LTE)	24
3.1.3 Results & discussion	25
3.1.3.1 Modeling EOM decomposition in laboratory conditions with Roth-C.....	25
3.1.3.2 Modeling SOC stocks in LTE with Roth-C	34
3.1.3.3 Pros and cons of each model version	39
3.1.4 Conclusion and recommendation.....	40
3.2. Effects of pH and liming on SOC decomposition rates	42
4. Assessment different biomass pathways via organic amendments on long-term SOC stocks	44
5. Conclusions.....	50
References.....	51

1. Introduction

Soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks depend not only on the quantity of C inputs, but also on their quality. Adding exogenous organic matter to the soil is one of the recognized agricultural practices to build up SOC stocks. However, the amount of agricultural biomass available for this purpose after food, feed and fiber production is limited. For example, crop residues such as straw can be used for energy production, incorporated into farmyard manure, pyrolyzed to produce biochar, or left on the land to contribute to soil organic carbon formation. Some crop residues and biomass can also be used in biogas plants and then partially returned to the soil as digestate. These different ways of using biomass have implications for SOC stocks and other soil properties, economic costs and benefits, as well as greenhouse gas emissions and soil ecosystem services.

This WP investigated the extent to which the processing of organic material incorporated into the soil affects SOC stocks. Specifically, the following processing methods and agricultural activities were considered: pyrolysis (biochar), composting and anaerobic digestion, and the addition of manure and sludge. We assessed the extent to which such treatment of biomass feedstocks can increase the stability of organic C and therefore potentially be used to increase SOC. Importantly, the overall sequestration efficiency, which takes into account C losses during biological processing or pyrolysis, was also addressed. In addition, the WP evaluated the role of liming for SOC sequestration.

It has been hypothesized that biomass pyrolysis is a very promising processing method for SOC sequestration, as it allows the addition of stabilized carbon to the soil (Wang, Xiong, and Kuzyakov 2016). As a result, relevant global sequestration potentials have been claimed for the conversion of crop residues into biochar (Karan et al. 2023). It is more uncertain and needs to be assessed whether other processing methods (composting and fermentation) can also reduce the turnover of the organic feedstock remaining after the process and lead to SOC sequestration. The potential to change the amount of organic amendments is limited because (i) it is closely linked to animal husbandry and stocking rates (manure) and compost feedstock collection, and (ii) most exogenous organic matter is already applied to agricultural soils. Therefore, only a change in turnover of organic amendments that exceeds respiration losses during processing can contribute to SOC sequestration and was therefore assessed in this WP. The main objectives of WP3 were to derive model parameters for selected amendments, to describe changes in C input stability and to discuss the usefulness of an emission factor approach.

Work package 3 of CarboSeq comprised four different tasks:

T 3.1 Biochar feedstock quality and model parametrization. The goal was to derive stability indicators for biochar amendment and to suggest how to implement biochar in SOC modelling. Biochar properties are largely dependent on feedstock and pyrolysis conditions (Li et al. 2019). The highest treatment temperature (HTT) during carbonization is an important production parameter that determines biochar properties, and biochars with enhanced resistance to decomposition can be obtained when carbonized above certain temperature thresholds (Budai et al. 2016). HTT is an important parameter during the production of stable biochars, but it is difficult to verify and is not the sole production parameter influencing the biochar product. As a result, different pyrolysis furnaces treating the same feedstock at a given temperature can result in biochars of different quality. The stability of biochar against decomposition in soil is closely related to its intrinsic chemical and physical properties and previous work initiated by the International Biochar Initiative (IBI) recommended the use of elemental ratios to verify biochar stability (IBI 2015). This approach has also been included in the EU regulation 2021/2088 (EU 2021).

Recent advances in understanding the role of feedstock (i.e. wood vs. straw) and pyrolysis conditions in defining biochar properties were evaluated with the aim of deriving a classification of biochar 'qualities' that can be used in simple (Tier 1-2) approaches and provide a basis for model parameterization in the RothC model (Tier 3). Recent and ongoing research indicates that measurable biochar properties are closely related to the stability of biochar once applied to soil, and may therefore assist in the parameterization of biochar for soil carbon modelling.

T 3.2 Abiotic and biotic drivers for biochar stability. Here we evaluated how biochar decomposition is influenced by external factors such as moisture, temperature, mode of incorporation of biochar into the soil matrix, soil texture, or pH to decide whether or not incorporating these properties as rate modifiers improve the soil carbon model. On the biological side, the presence or absence of fresh and mature non-pyrogenic soil OM may interact with biochar decomposition by stimulating or inhibiting microbial activity. Furthermore, the efficiency with which biochar is transformed to microbial biomass is a highly topical issue. A literature review of these factors provided information on whether their effect is quantifiable. The corresponding literature was reviewed to decide whether and how these factors should be considered as drivers in SOC modeling.

T 3.3 Other organic amendments. The goal was to improve the prediction of SOC storage by the application of other organic amendments, i.e. farmyard manure, slurry, sewage sludge, anaerobic digestate, or compost (also referred to as exogenous organic matter EOM).

Although organic amendments play a crucial role in many European farming systems in terms of nutrient recycling, the capacity to increase the amount of organic amendments (e.g., with increasing stocking rates) is limited. Therefore, this task focused in particular on the effect of the quality (in terms of stability against decomposition) of the organic amendments and the effects of switching between different types of amendments. The ongoing trend away from farmyard manure towards liquid manure or digestate may have implications for SOC storage. The available biomass may be used via different pathways in terms of SOC sequestration and the improvement of other soil functions. In this task, we derived improved parameters to model the stability of the different organic amendments and suggested how they can be incorporated into the RothC model. This will allow the investigation of the net effects of different pathways of biomass/organic matter management on long-term SOC sequestration, which may be influenced by the method of biomass transformation (e.g., composting, biogas plant conversion, pyrolysis, non-transformed residues).

T3.4 Effect of liming on soil carbon. Soil pH affects the structure, composition, and activities of microbial communities that drive SOC transformation as well as GHG fluxes from arable soils, such as nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions. Acidic soils cover about 40% of the world's arable land and are often associated with suboptimal plant growth. Liming with materials rich in calcium and magnesium carbonate is therefore a common agricultural practice to increase soil pH and crop yields. Liming could potentially be a management tool to mediate pH effects on SOC sequestration, but better understanding of resulting net effects is needed, e.g., to allow the integration of pH effects in predictive models of soil carbon sequestration. In this task, we collected empirical information on interactions between soil pH and dynamics of SOC changes in agricultural soils. We elucidated i) how SOC decomposition rates are affected by pH and ii) how plant inputs are modulated by pH. This information will be provided in a way that allows for the potential consideration of soil pH as a driver for SOC in the CarboSeq modeling framework.

The corresponding deliverables of WP3 were:

D#1 Biochar classification and C emission factors for each biochar class

D#2 Decomposition rate constants of biochar according to main (a)biotic drivers

D#3 Assessment of the impact of different biomass pathways via organic amendments on long-term SOC stocks

D#4 Report on the modelling of biochar and other organic amendments in RothC

D#5 Report on the modelling of pH and liming in RothC

This report represents the overall results of WP3, and all deliverables are described within this report. As the individual elements, i.e. tasks and deliverables, follow the same internal structure (i.e., stability of biochar and other exogeneous organic materials EOM), it was decided that separation into individual reports was not considered useful.

2. Biochar stability and modeling

The issue of biochar stability involves two related research questions: First, how much carbon from the initial feedstock ends up as biochar carbon, and second, how much of the carbon in biochar decomposes in the soil over time. These questions have been addressed through a combination of compiling and analyzing existing literature data and developing parameter values that reflect biochar stability as documented in decomposition studies.

2.1. Biochar feedstock quality, pyrolysis yield and biochar stability

Biochar decomposability is strongly determined by its physico-chemical properties, which themselves are mainly a function of i) the feedstock and ii) the pyrolysis conditions. For the purpose of CarboSeq, we distinguished two feedstock types, herbaceous-like materials such as grass/straw (hereafter referred to as non-woody NW) and woody (W). A literature search revealed 142 entries that reported feedstock type, pyrolysis temperature, pyrolysis yield, molar H/C_{org}-ratios, and C-contents of both the feedstock and the produced biochar within the same study (Table 1). This enabled us to evaluate the carbon yield of the process as well as the role of the H/C_{org} ratio in determining biochar stability. For our analysis, we only considered studies with biochar H/C_{org} ratios of < 0.7 and C_{org}-contents of ≥ 50 %, in line with the requirements of the European Biochar Certificate (EBC 2012-2022) and of the Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2088 on pyrolysis and gasification materials (EU 2021). They were used to derive the effect of feedstock and pyrolysis temperature on biochar quality and biochar yield (both on a dry mass and a carbon basis).

Table 1. Average properties of feedstocks and produced biochars used to estimate biochar yield and stability. Numbers are mean and values in parenthesis indicate one standard deviation (Rodrigues et al. 2023).

Feedstock type	Feedstock C-content (%)	Pyrol. Temp. (°C)	Biochar dry matter yield (%)	Biochar C _{org} -content (%)	Biochar C _{org} -yield (%)	Biochar H/C _{org} -ratio (-)	Biochar O/C _{org} -ratio (-)
Non-woody (n = 71)	48.7 (3.1)	595 (165)	31.5 (7.9)	77.7 (10.6)	48.6 (9.3)	0.35 (0.18)	0.14 (0.07)
Woody (n = 71)	49.0 (2.9)	602 (146)	27.0 (6.1)	79.9 (5.8)	43.6 (9.0)	0.37 (0.18)	0.11 (0.06)

We identified the H/C_{org} ratio as the most suitable parameter for predicting biochar stability, in line with Lehmann and Joseph (2015): biochars with lower H/C_{org} exhibit higher stability. Biochar's H/C_{org} ratio was a linear function of pyrolysis temperature (Fig. 1), with no difference between NW and W.

Fig. 1. Dependency of biochar H/C_{org} ratio on pyrolysis temperature for woody ($n=71$, black symbols), and non-woody ($n=71$, open symbols) materials. Line shows linear regression $y = a + b \cdot x$ with coefficients $a = 0.98 (\pm 0.03)$, $b = -0.0010 (0.00004)$; $R^2 = 0.79$ (Rodrigues et al. 2023)

In contrast to the H/C_{org} ratio, biochar C-yield was only loosely related to pyrolysis temperature (Fig. 2). This illustrates the combined effect of declining dry matter yields with temperature (Fig. 3) while at the same time C-contents of the produced biochar increase (Fig. 4).

Fig. 2. Dependency of biochar C-yield on pyrolysis temperature for woody (n=71, black symbols), and non-woody (n=69, open symbols) materials. Line shows polynomial function $y = a + (b/x)$ with coefficients $a = 37.0 (\pm 3.2)$, $b = 4913 (1750)$; $R^2 = 0.05$ (Rodrigues et al. 2023).

Fig. 3. Dependency of biochar dry matter yield on pyrolysis temperature for woody (n=71, black symbols), and non-woody (n=71, open symbols) materials. (Rodrigues et al. 2023)

Fig. 4. C_{org} -content of biochars produced at different temperatures for woody ($n=71$, black symbols), and non-woody ($n=71$, open symbols) materials. (Rodrigues et al. 2023)

Across all analyzed feedstocks and pyrolysis temperatures, biochar C-yield was 46.1 (± 9.4)%. The data above suggest that separating biochar just by herbaceous vs. woody feedstock does not improve the overall classification of its stability.

For many feedstocks, the average biochar C-yield correlated positively with the biochar's H/C_{org} ratio, i.e. higher yield coincides with biochar (Fig. 5). On average, C-yields decline by 1.7% (range 0.3%–4.0%) for a decrease of 0.1 in H/C_{org} .

It is remarkable that the feedstocks with highest C-yields of >45% are all agricultural residues (hazelnut kernel husk > olive husk > hazelnut shell > sugarcane > corn stover), while the woody feedstocks have overall lower yields of between 38 and 45% (Rodrigues et al. 2023).

Fig. 5. Biochar C-yield as a function of the biochar's H/C_{org} -ratio for 20 different feedstocks. Statistically significant slopes are marked with an asterisk (Rodrigues et al. 2023).

Biochar stability is defined as its resistance to decomposition after application to soil. In line with (IPCC 2019), we use the term F_{perm} , i.e. the fraction of biochar-C remaining in soil 100 years after its application and analyzed how it relates to the biochar's H/C_{org} ratio. Criteria for including studies were i) a minimum laboratory or field incubation of one year, ii) data availability that allowed fitting a 2-pool model to the decomposition data, iii) information on the H/C_{org} ratio of the respective biochars, iv) identification of decomposition rates by means of isotopic labeling or unique markers, and v) publication in a peer-reviewed form. Our literature review (Rodrigues et al. 2023) revealed 77 data points from 13 studies, encompassing one field experiment and 12 laboratory experiments. It encompasses data from 19 different feedstocks, that is six from woody materials, 11 from nonwoody and two from papermill sludge and poultry litter. The nonwoody feedstocks include grasses, straw and crop residues. F_{perm} was determined by fitting a two-pool exponential decay model to the data set.

Results reveal a strong non-linear response of F_{perm} to the H/C_{org} -ratio of the biochars (Fig. 6). Biochars with $H/C_{\text{org}} < 0.4$ have F_{perm} values of approximately 0.80, i.e., 80 % of the biochar can still be found in soil after 100 years of decomposition. The F_{perm} of biochars with higher H/C_{org} ratios approached values of < 0.20 .

Fig. 6. Relationship between the molar ratios of biochar hydrogen to organic carbon (H/C_{org}) and calculated fraction of biochar C remaining after 100 years (F_{perm}) for 77 data points from 13 studies with minimum duration of 1 year for a temperature of 14.9 °C (Rodrigues et al. 2023). Black line shows the best fit, dashed lines the 95% confidence interval of the regression line. Symbols refer to the corresponding references. R^2 refers to the adjusted coefficient of determination.

2.2. Modelling of biochar in RothC

The Rothamsted Carbon model RothC26.3 is widely used to simulate effects of management, land-use and climate on organic carbon stocks and dynamics in mineral soils, considering also the factors soil moisture, temperature, and clay content. Its structure is explained in Coleman and Jenkinson (1996). In CarboSeq, the model has been pre-selected based on its application in FAO GSOC (FAO 2022), to quantify management effects and sequestration potentials in European agriculture (WP 9). The kinetic pools in RothC comprise two plant litter pools (DPM, RPM) whose size distribution vary with vegetation type. Two other kinetic pools (BIO, HUM) describe the further decomposition of the organic matter. Stability of any organic material in RothC is determined by the pool specific decomposition rate constants, the distribution of the pool sizes of the incoming carbon, and the modulating factors temperature and moisture. Further transformation of the pools BIO and HUM, which are either formed during litter decomposition or already part of the added organic materials such as farmyard manure (FYM) also depends on the soil's clay content.

Decomposition rates and pool sizes of biochar for RothC

The decomposition of biochar in soil has been described using a two-pool model with exponential decay function as early as 2012 (Woolf and Lehmann 2012). In such a model, the amount of carbon in biochar, or other organic materials, is assigned to two different pools, each of them decomposing with their intrinsic rate constant and first order kinetics. More recent studies analyzed the most suitable decomposition model, based on comprehensive literature survey, and confirmed that two- or three pool models are well suited to describe biochar decomposition (Woolf et al. 2021). The data in Fig. 6 derive from such a two-pool model with parameters fitted to biochar decay rates in laboratory or field incubations.

To parameterize biochar decomposition, we therefore followed a concept that describes biochar as being composed of two C pools, a small labile and a large stable pool, which both decompose following first order kinetics with a respective intrinsic rate constant (Woolf and Lehmann 2012). Rather than to solely rely on data underlying Fig. 6, we extended the approach by using thermal stability parameters and the biochar's H/C_{org} ratio to derive the size of the small and labile pool. This approach has been described by Keel et al. (2023) and offers the advantage that no further time-consuming incubation studies are required.

The size of the smaller, labile biochar pool is estimated from the biochar properties thermal stability, H/C_{org} ratio and CO_2 release during one-year decomposition studies. It was shown based on incubation data (Zimmerman 2010) that the amount of C released during one year is closely related to the thermal stability of the biochar (Harvey et al. 2012). We used the

relationship between thermal stability and H/C_{org} ratio as shown in Keel et al. (2023). In this way it was possible, knowing H/C_{org} , to derive the size of the labile biochar pool BC1, and correspondingly that of the stable biochar pool $BC2 = 1 - BC1$ in Table 2 below. The decomposition rate constant $k1$ of the labile biochar pool is assigned to 10 yr^{-1} , following Keel et al. (2023). For the long-term effect of biochar on SOC, the rate constant $k2$ of the stable biochar pool BC2 is of greater importance. Here, a two-pool model with BC1, BC2, and $k1$ was fitted to match F_{perm} as shown in Fig. 6 for biochars of different H/C_{org} ratios:

$$F_{perm}(100) = BC1 \exp(-k1 \cdot t) + BC2 \exp(-k2 \cdot t)$$

with BC1 and BC2 being the sizes and $k1$ and $k2$ the decay rate constants of the labile and the stable pool, respectively. The corresponding parameter values are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Pool sizes (% of total C) of labile (BC1) and stable biochar carbon (BC2) and corresponding decomposition rate constants $k1$, $k2$, (yr^{-1}) for biochars with different H/C_{org} ratios. Rate constants are shown for a mean annual temperature of $9.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (calculated from data in Fig. 6 using the temperature response function of RothC).

H/C_{org} ratio	< 0.1	0.1-0.2	0.2-0.3	0.3-0.4	0.4-0.5	0.5-0.6	0.6-0.7
BC1	0.3	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.6
BC2	99.7	99.2	99.0	98.8	98.7	98.6	98.4
$k1$	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
$k2$	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008	0.0010	0.0017	0.0038

The sizes of the labile pool are smaller than the estimate of 5–10% in a previous study (Woolf and Lehmann 2012); however, some of the studies from which these authors had derived pool sizes utilized more labile biochars, i.e. biochars produced at lower temperatures. The approach followed by Keel et al. (2023), instead, provides a universal analytical measure for estimating the labile pool size.

For the long-term effect of biochar addition to soil, the parameter $k2$ is of particular relevance. Our estimate of $0.0008 / \text{yr}$ for biochars with H/C_{org} of ≤ 0.4 is in a similar order of magnitude as previously reported (Woolf and Lehmann 2012; Kuzyakov, Bogomolova, and Glaser 2014; Lehmann et al. 2015; Jiang et al. 2016), considering also the different underlying soil temperatures. The advantage of the approach presented here is that all relevant parameters for simulating biochar decomposition can be derived from just the molar H/C_{org} ratio, allowing the parameters to reflect the biochar stability at hand.

2.3. Biochar classification and C emission factors

The results above indicate that the biochar's H/C_{org} ratio can serve as a reliable indicator of biochar stability. It is therefore suggested to use that indicator for biochar classification in the context of long-term stability in soil. As the long-term sequestration induced by adding biochar primarily depends on the biochar's stability as well as on the C yield of pyrolysis, combining these two properties gives C emission factors. We define a 100-years C emission factor for biochar addition as

$$EF_{biochar100} = F_{perm} \times C_{yield}$$

where C_{yield} is the C yield of the pyrolysis. This way of calculation equals the term 'carbon sequestration efficiency' *in sensu* Rodrigues et al. (2023) and takes into account i) C losses from the initial processing (here: pyrolysis) and ii) a calculated time-horizon of 100 years, following the F_{perm} concept of (IPCC 2019). Table 3 provides the corresponding default values along the gradient of studied H/C_{org} ratios. For example, pyrolyzing 1 t biomass-C yields 0.461 t biochar-C. For a H/C_{org} of 0.25, 91 % of that 0.461 t C is still in soil after 100 years; leading to an overall $EF_{biochar100}$ of 0.42.

Table 3. Biochar emission factor $EF_{biochar100}$ and corresponding F_{perm} values for different classes of H/C_{org} ratios for a soil temperature of 9.3 °C, calculated based on a C-yield of pyrolysis of 46.1 %.

H/C_{org} ratio	< 0.1	0.1-0.2	0.2-0.3	0.3-0.4	0.4-0.5	0.5-0.6	0.6-0.7
F_{perm}	0.92	0.92	0.91	0.91	0.89	0.83	0.68
$EF_{biochar100}$	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.41	0.38	0.31

2.4. Biochar applied in Europe

The average biochar applied in Europe, based on data from the EBC certification (Ithaka-Institute 2024), has a mean (\pm 95% CI) H/C_{org} of 0.18 ± 0.04 (Fig. 7). It therefore corresponds to the second class of biochar stabilities in Table 2. For that H/C_{org} -range of 0.12 – 0.22, the C-yields of pyrolysis are 45.3 ± 2.7 (based on (Rodrigues et al. 2023)). The corresponding

C_{org} -contents are 80.8 % (± 17.4) (Fig. 7). Mean values were calculated from ln-transformed data. These numbers were derived from 92 (H/C_{org}) and 90 (C_{org} -content) batches from the EBC certification with batch sizes of on average 1048 tons produced biochar.

Fig. 7. Histograms of H/C_{org} ratios (left) and C_{org} content (right) from biochar samples from the EBC database (Ithaka-Institute 2024).

According to the same source, the amount of EBC-certified biochar in Europe (EU+EFTA) was approximately 64×10^3 (sixty-four thousand) tons using 261×10^3 tons of biomass. The biochar contained a total of 53×10^3 tons of carbon (Ithaka-Institute 2024). The actual production might be higher as not all biochar undergoes EBC-certification.

2.5. The importance of abiotic and biotic drivers for biochar stability

The stability of biochar against microbial decomposition in soil depends, primarily, on its intrinsic physical and chemical properties, which in turn largely depend on feedstock and pyrolysis conditions (i.e., pyrolysis temperature and retention time). Compared to plant residues, native soil organic matter, and other organic amendments, biochar is much less responsive to external factors. Nonetheless, the decomposition of biochar in soil may also be influenced by abiotic and biotic external factors, especially soil texture, temperature, moisture, pH, and co-amendments.

Most of the information available in the literature on the abiotic and biotic external drivers of biochar stability is reported in studies whose main purpose is to examine the effects of feedstock and pyrolysis conditions on CO_2 evolved from biochar-amended soils. The experiments reported in these studies are mostly conducted under controlled incubation

conditions at constant temperature, and field data are scarce. Meta-analyses of these studies have shown that the duration of the experiment is the most important factor affecting the derived biochar decomposition rates, particularly the longer the experiment the smaller the decomposition rate (Wang, Xiong, and Kuzyakov 2016; Chao, Zhang, and Wang 2018). This fact, together with the scarcity of data distinguishing between CO₂ released from biochar and native soil organic matter (using ¹³C or ¹⁴C isotopes), would make any new parametrization for the modulation of biochar decomposition by external factors highly uncertain and unreliable at the moment. Nonetheless, the information currently available in the literature may provide some insights into the sign of the effects, as detailed below.

Soil texture may affect biochar stability in soil by influencing the physical accessibility and oxygen diffusion needed for microbial decomposition. In general, the coarser the soil, the higher the oxygen diffusion, the lower the organic-mineral associations, and the higher the physical accessibility of microbes to the organic substrates. Consistently with these mechanisms, a number of studies show that the rate of biochar decomposition increases with decreasing clay content (Bruun et al. 2014; Wang, Xiong, and Kuzyakov 2016; Yang et al. 2022). However, there is also meta-analytic evidence in the literature showing that biochar does not decompose significantly faster in coarse soils than in fine soils (Chao, Zhang, and Wang 2018).

Most studies show that biochar decomposition increases with increasing soil temperature, and under unsaturated wet conditions compared to waterlogged and dry environments, due to higher microbial activity (Nguyen and Lehmann 2009; Wang, Xiong, and Kuzyakov 2016; Chao, Zhang, and Wang 2018; Chen, Lin, et al. 2022; Zhang, Dang, et al. 2022). Soil temperature and moisture have been also suggested to play a role in biochar stability through freezing-thawing and swelling-shrinking effects that reduce the size of biochar particles and thereby increase its microbial decomposability (Wang, Xiong, and Kuzyakov 2016). Direct temperature and moisture effects are considered in the RothC model. Indirect effects through freezing-thawing and swelling-shrinking effects are not considered and cannot be implemented as this would require a completely new model with a soil physics submodule.

Soil pH influences microbial activity and nutrient availability for organic matter decomposition. Thus, biochar decomposition in soil has been found to increase with increasing pH from acidic to neutral values (Luo et al. 2011; Chao, Zhang, and Wang 2018).

Finally, the incorporation of labile organic compounds derived from organic co-amendments, plant residues and microbial and root exudates into the soil may stimulate biochar decomposition through co-metabolism (Kuzyakov et al. 2009; Luo et al. 2011; Keith, Singh, and Singh 2011; Ventura et al. 2019; Ventura et al. 2015; Schimmelpfennig et al. 2017;

Speratti et al. 2018; Fang et al. 2019). Increasing soil N and other plant and microbial nutrient contents in low fertility soils may also be expected to slightly increase the rate of biochar decomposition, but the evidence in the literature for this effect is weak (Lu et al. 2015; Chao, Zhang, and Wang 2018)

3. Methodology to calibrate and validate C inputs and stability from other organic amendments

In its original version, only farmyard manure (FYM) has default parameters in Roth-C. Many authors proposed to modify these default parameters for simulating other exogenous organic matter (EOM) and different types FYM to accommodate the huge variability in EOM characteristics. The possible modifications are the allocation of EOM C between RPM, DPM, HUM and IOM and the identification of specific decomposition rates for EOM pools (Table 4).

3.1. Modelling of other organic amendments in RothC

For simulating EOM C mineralization during laboratory incubation, modelers usually optimized Roth-C decomposition parameters to match observed C mineralization (Gasser et al. 2022; Mondini et al. 2017; Smith et al. 2014) (Table 4). For simulating SOC stocks in the field, modelers used different calibration approaches:

1. They *a priori* use the default Roth-C parameters for farmyard manure (partitioning factor and decomposition rate) when no specific information is found in the study (Jha et al. 2021; Kamoni et al. 2007).
2. They calibrate EOM parameters to match observed SOC stocks (Cagnarini et al. 2019; Dechow et al. 2019; Farina et al. 2018; Peltre et al. 2012).
3. They calibrate EOM parameters based on EOM characteristics (Leifeld, Reiser, and Oberholzer 2009; Doblás-Rodrigo et al. 2023; Mao et al. 2022; Mondini, Coleman, and Whitmore 2012; Peltre et al. 2012; Tits et al. 2014).
4. They calibrate EOM parameters to match observed EOM C mineralization in laboratory incubation (when EOM applied in the fields are also incubated in the lab) (Smith et al. 2014).

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

Despite these existing studies and approaches, the performance for the simulation of SOC stocks of the different “model versions” (variable allocation of EOM C, fixed (standard) or optimized decomposition rates) has not been comparatively evaluated, and EOM parameters for a wide range of EOM types have still to be proposed. Therefore, the objectives of this work were to determine the best model version for simulating SOC stocks after repeated EOM applications and to provide Roth-C parameters for different EOM types.

Table 4: Examples of studies using Roth-C for simulating C dynamics after EOM application.

Study	Type of EOM	Source of data	EOM modified parameters				Calibration methods
			Pool sizes			Decomposition rates	
			DPM & RPM	HUM	IOM		
(Cagnarini et al. 2019)	Farmyard manure	Field	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Matching field data
(Dechow et al. 2019)	Farmyard manure, sludge, compost, peat, sawdust, slurry	Field	Yes	Yes	No	No	Matching field data
(Doblas-Rodrigo et al. 2023)	11 organic amendments from livestock farms	Field	Yes	Yes	No	No	Deriving from EOM characteristics
(Farina et al. 2018)	MSW compost	Field	Yes	No	No	No	Matching field data
(Gasser et al. 2022)	Manure, slurry, digestate	Lab	Yes	Yes	No	No	Matching lab incubation data
(Jha et al. 2021)	Manure	Field	No	No	No	No	Default Roth-C parameters
(Kamoni et al. 2007)	Manure	Field	No	No	No	No	Default Roth-C parameters
(Leifeld, Reiser, and Oberholzer 2009)	Manure, composted manure	Field	Yes	Yes	No	No	Match loss during FYM storage
(Mao et al. 2022)	Paper crumble	Field	Yes	No	No	No	Deriving from EOM characteristics (thermogravimetry)
(Mondini, Coleman, and Whitmore 2012)	Green waste compost	Field	Yes	No	No	No	Deriving from EOM characteristics

(Mondini et al. 2017)	Composts, digestates, manures, bioenergy byproducts, animal residues, agro-industrial wastes, sludges	Lab	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Matching lab incubation data
(Peltre et al. 2012)	Composts, manures, sludges, sawdust, peat	Field	Yes	Yes	No	No	Matching field data / Deriving from EOM characteristics
(Smith et al. 2014)	Digestate, compost, biochar	Lab + field	Yes	Yes	Yes (biochar)	No	Matching lab incubation data
(Tits et al. 2014)	Vegetable, fruit and garden waste	Field	Yes	No	No	No	Deriving from EOM characteristics

3.1.1 Material & Methods

3.1.2.1 Roth C model versions

Four different model versions of Roth-C were tested:

- EOM C allocated to 2 pools of OM (DPM and RPM), with fixed (standard) decomposition rates
- EOM C allocated to 2 pools of OM (DPM and RPM), with variable (optimized) decomposition rates
- EOM C allocated to 3 pools of OM (DPM, RPM and HUM), with fixed (standard) decomposition rates
- EOM C allocated to 3 pools of OM (DPM, RPM and HUM), with variable (optimized) decomposition rates

The fixed/standard decomposition rates for FYM in RothC are 10, 0.3 and 0.02 yr⁻¹ for DPM, RPM and HUM, respectively, and the corresponding pool sizes 0.49, 0.49, and 0.02. Except this different allocation of EOM C, the standard Roth-C (Coleman and Jenkinson 1996) was used. The different model versions were coded in R.

3.1.2.2 Laboratory incubation database

The EOM laboratory incubation database presented in Levavasseur et al. (2022) was used. The database contains information about EOM type (56 types), EOM characteristics (e.g., C and N content) and C and N mineralization data in controlled laboratory conditions. Only C mineralization data were used in this study. In comparison to Levavasseur et al. (2022), additional EOM types were added from recent research projects and the database finally contained 734 EOMs.

3.1.2.3 Long term field experiment database

In this study, we considered the QualiAgro, the Colmar, and the Ultuna long-term field experiments (LTE) (Noirot-Cosson et al. 2016; Chen, Levavasseur, et al. 2022; Gerzabek et al. 1997). Management data, SOC stocks, soil and climate data were used in Roth-C. The experiments differ in terms of soil, climate, crops, EOM type and EOM application rates. More information about these LTE can be found in the abovementioned papers.

In QualiAgro and Colmar, the same EOM as applied in the field were also incubated under controlled conditions and the mineralization data are contained in the laboratory incubation database (section 3.1.2.2).

Table 5: Main characteristics of the LTE used in this study

LTE	Soil type	Climate	EOM type considered	Period considered
QualiAgro	Luvisol	Oceanic	GWS: Green waste and sewage sludge compost BIO: Green waste and food waste compost MSW: Compost of municipal solid waste FYM: Bovine solid manure	1998-2021
Colmar	Calcisol	Semi-continental	SLU: Urban sludge GWS: Green waste and sewage sludge compost BIO: Green waste and food waste compost FYM: Bovine solid manure FYMC: Composted bovine solid manure	2000-2018
Ultuna	Eutric Cambisol	Continental	FYM: Bovine solid manure SLU: Urban sludge PEAT: Peat SAWDUST: Sawdust	1956-2007

3.1.2.3 Simulation of lab mineralization data

We simulated the remaining EOM-C over time in the laboratory incubations with the different model versions. The EOM parameters were optimized to minimize the sum of squared differences between the observed and simulated remaining C. The optimization was performed in R with the ‘‘optim’’ function and the ‘‘L-BFGS-B’’ method (Byrd et al. 1995). Mean error (ME), root mean square error (RMSE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2) were used to assess the model performance for simulating the remaining C.

3.1.2.4 Simulation of Long-term experiments (LTE)

We simulated the evolution of SOC stocks in both EOM and control treatments in each LTE and with each model version. We also computed the differences in SOC stocks between the EOM treatments and the control treatment (Δ SOC). We tested three different approaches for the calibration of EOM parameters:

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

1. Calibration based on field data: EOM parameters were optimized to minimize the sum of squared differences between the observed and simulated Δ SOC
2. Calibration based on lab mineralization data, with parameters specific to the EOM applied in the field (for LTE with lab incubation data, i.e., QualiAgro and Colmar)
3. Calibration based on lab mineralization data from EOM laboratory incubation database (section 3.1.2.2), with mean parameters for the applied EOM type (for LTE without lab incubation data, i.e. Ultuna)

For the calibration based on field data, the optimization was performed in R with the "optim" function and the "L-BFGS-B" method (Byrd et al. 1995). Mean error (ME), root mean square error (RMSE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2) were used to assess the model performance for simulating Δ SOC.

3.1.3 Results & discussion

3.1.3.1 Modeling EOM decomposition in laboratory conditions with Roth-C

3.1.3.1.1 Performances of the different model versions

The two pools model with fixed decomposition rates had the lowest performances for simulating the EOM remaining C during laboratory incubations (Figure 8, Table 6), with ME, RMSE and R^2 equal to -0.004 mg C/mg added C, 0.033 mg C/mg added C and 0.96, respectively. However, these performances were still quite good compared to published results (Levassasseur et al. 2022; Mondini et al. 2017). The other three models performed similarly and slightly better than the two pools model with fixed decomposition rates.

Figure 8: Observed against simulated remaining C during laboratory incubations, according to the Roth-C model version. Each point represents the remaining EOM C for a specific EOM and specific incubation day.

Table 6. Roth-C performances for simulating EOM remaining C during laboratory incubations, according to the Roth-C model version. ME, RMSE and R² are the mean values for all EOM incubations.

Model version	ME (mg remaining C/mg added C)	RMSE (mg remaining C/mg added C)	R ²
2 pools, fixed decomposition rates	-0.004	0.033	0.96
2 pools, optimized decomposition rates	-0.003	0.009	1.00
3 pools, fixed decomposition rates	0.000	0.012	0.99
3 pools, optimized decomposition rates	0.001	0.016	0.99

3.1.3.1.2 Optimized decomposition parameters per EOM type

The mean optimized EOM parameters per EOM type and for each model version are summarized in Tables 7 (two-pool model) and 8 (three-pool model).

Table 7. Mean EOM parameters per EOM type for an allocation of EOM-C to DPM and RPM only (two-pool model), with fixed or optimized decomposition rates where f = fraction, i.e., pool size, k = decomposition rate constant yr⁻¹.

EOM_group	EOM_type	EOM number	Optimized partitioning factors and fixed decomposition rates		Optimized partitioning factors and decomposition rates			
			f.DPM	f.RPM	k.DPM	k.RPM	f.DPM	f.RPM
Animal manure	Bovine slurry	3	0.31	0.69	15.2	0.11	0.37	0.63
	Bovine solid manure	57	0.15	0.85	7.3	0.16	0.25	0.75
	Chicken droppings	5	0.62	0.38	17.0	0.24	0.61	0.39
	Chicken manure	21	0.25	0.75	14.5	0.16	0.30	0.70
	Dried chicken droppings	2	0.35	0.65	14.4	0.11	0.44	0.56
	Horse manure	8	0.36	0.64	5.9	0.11	0.49	0.51
	Other animal manure	8	0.29	0.71	11.0	0.15	0.36	0.64
	Pig manure	6	0.10	0.90	9.6	0.16	0.17	0.83
	Pig slurry	11	0.37	0.63	15.7	0.27	0.38	0.62
	Sheep manure	1	0.22	0.78	2.6	0.10	0.46	0.54
Animal residue	Solid phase of pig slurry	7	0.19	0.81	10.6	0.14	0.28	0.72
	Feather meal	2	0.43	0.57	9.0	0.10	0.50	0.50
	Guano	2	0.81	0.19	18.6	0.31	0.74	0.26
Compost	Other animal residue	4	0.67	0.33	8.8	0.40	0.73	0.27
	Composted bovine solid manure	19	0.04	0.96	7.5	0.12	0.13	0.87
	Composted chicken droppings	3	0.31	0.69	10.5	0.18	0.35	0.65
	Composted chicken manure	4	0.41	0.59	15.0	0.23	0.41	0.59
	Composted goat manure	2	0.17	0.83	6.0	0.10	0.29	0.71
	Composted horse manure	6	0.05	0.96	11.6	0.10	0.09	0.91
	Composted pig manure	8	0.03	0.97	10.5	0.14	0.07	0.93
Composted pig slurry and vegetal residues	17	0.06	0.94	9.0	0.13	0.10	0.90	

EOM_group	EOM_type	EOM number	Optimized partitioning factors and fixed decomposition rates		Optimized partitioning factors and decomposition rates			
			f.DPM	f.RPM	k.DPM	k.RPM	f.DPM	f.RPM
	Composted sheep manure	2	0.13	0.87	5.6	0.10	0.26	0.74
	Composted solid phase of digestate	2	0.00	1.00	10.2	0.12	0.04	0.96
	Green waste and biowaste compost	56	0.04	0.96	15.0	0.14	0.09	0.91
	Green waste and bovine manure compost	2	0.12	0.88	20.0	0.14	0.18	0.82
	Green waste and chicken droppings compost	3	0.19	0.82	11.6	0.12	0.26	0.74
	Green waste and sludge compost	76	0.03	0.97	15.2	0.16	0.07	0.93
	Green waste compost	24	0.03	0.97	14.0	0.11	0.08	0.92
	Municipal solid waste compost	97	0.24	0.76	12.9	0.17	0.29	0.71
	Other Compost	32	0.09	0.91	11.8	0.13	0.17	0.83
Digestate	Digestate of bovine manure (dry AD)	6	0.00	1.00	16.6	0.10	0.05	0.95
	Liquid phase of digestate of biowaste and other wastes	2	0.16	0.84	20.0	0.11	0.25	0.75
	Liquid phase of digestate of cover crops and other wastes	2	0.34	0.66	20.0	0.21	0.34	0.66
	Liquid phase of digestate of livestock effluents and other wastes	5	0.17	0.83	15.2	0.10	0.26	0.74
	Other digestate	15	0.11	0.89	14.9	0.16	0.17	0.83
	Raw digestate of biowaste and other wastes	7	0.26	0.74	13.7	0.24	0.28	0.72
	Raw digestate of cover crops and other wastes	14	0.27	0.73	19.1	0.20	0.29	0.71
	Raw digestate of livestock effluents and other wastes	14	0.19	0.81	14.5	0.10	0.26	0.74
	Raw digestate of municipal solid waste	2	0.01	0.99	15.6	0.10	0.12	0.88
	Solid phase of digestate of biowaste and other wastes	2	0.00	1.00	6.8	0.14	0.10	0.90
	Solid phase of digestate of cover crops and other wastes	3	0.10	0.90	11.4	0.10	0.18	0.82
Solid phase of digestate of livestock effluents and other wastes	6	0.19	0.82	4.0	0.10	0.38	0.62	
Others	Agro-industrial wastewater	23	0.56	0.44	18.5	0.25	0.57	0.43
	Commercial organic fertilizer	11	0.70	0.30	17.2	0.46	0.65	0.35
	Molasse	2	0.53	0.47	11.4	0.40	0.60	0.40

EOM_group	EOM_type	EOM number	Optimized partitioning factors and fixed decomposition rates		Optimized partitioning factors and decomposition rates			
			f.DPM	f.RPM	k.DPM	k.RPM	f.DPM	f.RPM
	Others	26	0.31	0.69	13.1	0.25	0.34	0.66
	Sugar beet vinasse	8	0.71	0.29	20.0	0.19	0.68	0.32
	Agro-industrial sludge	9	0.27	0.73	19.0	0.11	0.33	0.67
Sludge	Dried urban sewage sludge	17	0.39	0.61	15.6	0.29	0.40	0.60
	Limed urban sewage sludge	13	0.43	0.57	13.2	0.26	0.45	0.55
	Other sludge	6	0.25	0.75	15.7	0.20	0.29	0.71
	Paper mill sludge	2	0.13	0.87	12.5	0.14	0.20	0.80
	Urban sewage sludge	26	0.36	0.64	15.5	0.22	0.39	0.61
	Algae	5	0.84	0.16	17.6	0.54	0.78	0.22
Vegetal residue	Bark	5	0.06	0.94	3.3	0.11	0.29	0.71
	Other vegetal residue	13	0.17	0.83	12.7	0.16	0.26	0.74

Table 8. Mean EOM parameters per EOM type with an allocation of EOM C to DPM, RPM and HUM (three-pool model), with fixed or optimized decomposition rates.

EOM_group	EOM_type	EOM number	Fixed decomposition rates			Optimized decomposition rates				
			f.DP M	f.RPM	f.HUM	k.DPM	k.RPM	f.DPM	f.RPM	f.HUM
Animal manure	Bovine slurry	3	0.41	0.09	0.50	14.6	0.31	0.39	0.18	0.44
	Bovine solid manure	57	0.20	0.49	0.31	6.0	0.51	0.27	0.24	0.48
	Chicken droppings	5	0.66	0.14	0.20	17.2	0.48	0.61	0.23	0.16
	Chicken manure	21	0.33	0.19	0.47	14.1	0.46	0.31	0.28	0.41
	Dried chicken droppings	2	0.47	0.08	0.45	11.7	0.70	0.45	0.07	0.48

EOM_group	EOM_type	EOM number	Fixed decomposition rates			Optimized decomposition rates				
			f.DP M	f.RPM	f.HUM	k.DPM	k.RPM	f.DPM	f.RPM	f.HUM
	Horse manure	8	0.38	0.50	0.12	5.6	0.34	0.51	0.22	0.27
	Other animal manure	8	0.34	0.42	0.24	11.5	0.61	0.35	0.18	0.47
	Pig manure	6	0.14	0.45	0.41	8.8	0.56	0.21	0.14	0.66
	Pig slurry	11	0.44	0.27	0.29	16.1	0.59	0.38	0.27	0.35
	Sheep manure	1	0.22	0.78	0.00	2.2	0.10	0.54	0.00	0.46
	Solid phase of pig slurry	7	0.22	0.44	0.34	10.1	0.37	0.29	0.25	0.46
	Feather meal	2	0.51	0.12	0.37	7.5	0.40	0.55	0.00	0.45
Animal residue	Guano	2	0.83	0.00	0.17	18.6	0.31	0.74	0.18	0.08
	Other animal residue	4	0.69	0.21	0.11	8.7	0.70	0.73	0.06	0.20
Compost	Composted bovine solid manure	19	0.09	0.46	0.44	7.0	0.58	0.16	0.16	0.68
	Composted chicken droppings	3	0.35	0.38	0.27	11.3	0.53	0.33	0.36	0.31
	Composted chicken manure	4	0.46	0.09	0.44	15.1	0.50	0.41	0.26	0.33
	Composted goat manure	2	0.23	0.49	0.29	5.7	0.70	0.30	0.11	0.60
	Composted horse manure	6	0.08	0.25	0.67	8.6	0.61	0.12	0.07	0.82
	Composted pig manure	8	0.07	0.40	0.53	9.0	0.50	0.09	0.35	0.55
	Composted pig slurry and vegetal residues	17	0.09	0.27	0.64	10.8	0.29	0.11	0.27	0.61
	Composted sheep manure	2	0.19	0.49	0.31	4.5	0.70	0.30	0.04	0.66
	Composted solid phase of digestate	2	0.04	0.35	0.61	12.1	0.70	0.03	0.19	0.78
	Green waste and biowaste compost	56	0.11	0.29	0.61	12.9	0.45	0.10	0.29	0.61
	Green waste and bovine manure compost	2	0.21	0.21	0.57	20.0	0.14	0.18	0.82	0.00
	Green waste and chicken droppings compost	3	0.27	0.23	0.49	14.6	0.55	0.25	0.25	0.50
	Green waste and sludge compost	76	0.09	0.36	0.55	14.5	0.36	0.08	0.47	0.45
	Green waste compost	24	0.07	0.25	0.69	10.8	0.42	0.10	0.13	0.77
	Municipal solid waste compost	97	0.31	0.21	0.48	11.9	0.50	0.29	0.24	0.46
Other Compost	32	0.14	0.38	0.47	13.2	0.50	0.18	0.31	0.51	

EOM_group	EOM_type	EOM number	Fixed decomposition rates			Optimized decomposition rates				
			f.DP M	f.RPM	f.HUM	k.DPM	k.RPM	f.DPM	f.RPM	f.HUM
Digestate	Digestate of bovine manure (dry AD)	6	0.07	0.21	0.72	7.5	0.22	0.08	0.35	0.56
	Liquid phase of digestate of biowaste and other wastes	2	0.31	0.02	0.68	20.0	0.70	0.27	0.08	0.65
	Liquid phase of digestate of cover crops and other wastes	2	0.42	0.09	0.49	20.0	0.45	0.34	0.45	0.21
	Liquid phase of digestate of livestock effluents and other wastes	5	0.29	0.11	0.60	14.7	0.46	0.26	0.16	0.57
	Other digestate	15	0.19	0.25	0.57	13.1	0.35	0.21	0.19	0.61
	Raw digestate of biowaste and other wastes	7	0.32	0.40	0.28	13.6	0.50	0.29	0.37	0.34
	Raw digestate of cover crops and other wastes	14	0.36	0.12	0.53	19.1	0.62	0.29	0.27	0.44
	Raw digestate of livestock effluents and other wastes	14	0.28	0.17	0.55	14.5	0.57	0.27	0.09	0.64
	Raw digestate of municipal solid waste	2	0.14	0.14	0.72	14.6	0.40	0.13	0.31	0.56
	Solid phase of digestate of biowaste and other wastes	2	0.07	0.50	0.43	8.4	0.62	0.08	0.29	0.63
	Solid phase of digestate of cover crops and other wastes	3	0.20	0.13	0.67	9.0	0.70	0.21	0.04	0.75
Solid phase of digestate of livestock effluents and other wastes	6	0.22	0.61	0.17	3.4	0.59	0.41	0.11	0.47	
Others	Agro-industrial wastewater	23	0.62	0.04	0.34	18.1	0.40	0.58	0.09	0.33
	Commercial organic fertilizer	11	0.74	0.09	0.17	17.4	0.60	0.65	0.22	0.14
	Molasse	2	0.57	0.21	0.22	10.9	0.70	0.61	0.05	0.34
	Others	26	0.35	0.33	0.32	13.1	0.40	0.33	0.43	0.24
	Sugar beet vinasse	8	0.75	0.02	0.23	20.0	0.42	0.68	0.16	0.17
Sludge	Agro-industrial sludge	9	0.39	0.00	0.61	16.2	0.44	0.36	0.02	0.62
	Dried urban sewage sludge	17	0.45	0.25	0.31	16.1	0.45	0.39	0.43	0.18
	Limed urban sewage sludge	13	0.48	0.26	0.26	13.1	0.58	0.44	0.25	0.31
	Other sludge	6	0.33	0.30	0.38	16.3	0.65	0.28	0.30	0.42
	Paper mill sludge	2	0.21	0.31	0.48	12.5	0.14	0.20	0.80	0.00
	Urban sewage sludge	26	0.43	0.15	0.41	15.1	0.44	0.39	0.28	0.32
Vegetal residue	Algae	5	0.84	0.11	0.05	17.6	0.59	0.78	0.19	0.02
	Bark	5	0.14	0.54	0.31	5.8	0.68	0.24	0.24	0.51

EOM_group	EOM_type	EOM number	Fixed decomposition rates			Optimized decomposition rates				
			f.DP M	f.RPM	f.HUM	k.DPM	k.RPM	f.DPM	f.RPM	f.HUM
	Other vegetal residue	13	0.26	0.34	0.40	14.4	0.57	0.23	0.26	0.51

3.1.3.2 Modeling SOC stocks in LTE with Roth-C

3.1.3.2.1 Simulated evolution of Δ SOC: example of the BIO+N treatment in QualiAgro and Colmar

We focused on the simulated evolution of Δ SOC in the treatment with compost of green waste and food waste (BIO) and mineral N addition (BIO+N), present in both QualiAgro and Colmar (Figure 9). In both LTE, the evolution of Δ SOC was better simulated with a calibration of EOM parameters based on field data, which was expected. However, the two-pool model with fixed decomposition rates underestimated Δ SOC in the long term in QualiAgro, while it simulated well the evolution of Δ SOC in Colmar. The three other models (i.e. the two-pool model with optimized rates and the two three-pool models) simulated well the evolution of Δ SOC in both LTEs.

With a calibration based on laboratory incubation data specific to the EOM applied in the field, the performance of the prediction of the evolution of Δ SOC decreased, except with the two pools models and optimized decomposition rates in QualiAgro and the two-pool models and fixed decomposition rates in Colmar.

The calibration based on mean EOM parameters per EOM type seemed to yield similar results than a calibration based on laboratory incubation data specific to the EOM applied in the field.

QUALIAGRO

COLMAR

Calibration based on field data

Calibration based on lab incubation data (specific to the EOM applied in the field)

Calibration based on lab incubation data (mean EOM parameters for the EOM types)

Figure 9: Simulated and observed Δ SOC stocks in the BIO+N treatment in Qualiagro and Colmar, depending on the model version and on the calibration method

3.1.3.2 Observed and simulated Δ SOC stocks in all treatments of the three LTE

The relationship between measured and simulated Δ SOC in all LTEs for any model version and calibration method is reported in Figure 10. With a calibration of EOM parameters based on field data, the performances of the different model versions for simulating Δ SOC were good, with a median absolute ME lower than 0.5 t C/ha and a median RMSE lower or equal to 2 t C/ha for the three LTE. The R^2 values were higher than 0.8 for QualiAgro and Ultuna, and slightly lower for Colmar (from 0.66 to 0.79 depending on the model version), but with a lower variability for this LTE. These performances were good and similar to published results (Dechow et al. 2019; Karhu et al. 2012; Levavasseur et al. 2020; Peltre et al. 2012). The model version with 2 pools and fixed k had slightly lower performances in QualiAgro and Ultuna (for PEAT only, Figure 10) compared with the other model versions. It did not allow for a reliable simulation of the high increase in SOC stocks observed in these LTEs.

With a calibration based on laboratory mineralization data, either with specific parameters to the EOM applied in the field or with mean parameters for the considered EOM type, the performances of the model logically decreased compared to a calibration based on field data. As also expected, the performances were slightly lower with EOM mean parameters in comparison to specific EOM parameters.

Moreover, the performances varied with model complexity (Fig. 11). Increasing the model complexity led to higher mean errors. For example, in QualiAgro, RMSE was equal to 3.0, 3.6, 5.6 and 5.2 t C/ha for the models based on 2 pools and fixed k, 2 pools and optimized k, 3 pools and fixed k, and 3 pools and optimized k, respectively. This is reflected by the fact the three more complex models tended to overestimate Δ SOC in amended soils. On the other hand, increasing complexity enhanced R^2 for QualiAgro and Colmar.

Figure 10: Simulated and observed Δ SOC stocks for each treatment of QualiAgro, Colmar and Utuna, depending on the model version and on the calibration method (see Table 5 for meaning of the treatment).

Fig. 11. Performances of Roth-C for the simulation of Δ SOC stocks in QualiAgro, Colmar and Ultuna, depending on the model version and on the method of calibration. The boxplots represent the variability of ME, RMSE and R^2 for all the treatments together. For Ultuna, only the treatments with bovine manure and sludge are considered (peat and sawdust not simulated with the lab calibration approach)

3.1.3.3 Pros and cons of each model version

We summarized the simulation performances of the different model versions for lab mineralization data and field SOC stocks in Table 9. Considering the simulation of lab

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

mineralization data, the simplest model showed slightly lower performances than the more complex models, whose results were similar to each other.

The specific model version that stands out as the best one to simulate SOC stocks in amended soils depends on the calibration procedure. The simplest model (2 pools, fixed decomposition rates) had the best performance for simulating the SOC stocks when the model was calibrated with laboratory data (either specific mineralization data or mean data). We could thus recommend using this model version for users who want to simulate SOC stocks without field data available for the calibration of EOM parameters. However, we showed that this simplest model had lower performances for simulating SOC stocks as compared to a calibration based on field SOC data. In that case, the model with 2 pools and optimized decomposition rates or with 3 pools and fixed decomposition rates can be used.

Table 9. Pros and cons of each model version based on simulation results for laboratory mineralization data (734 EOM) and field SOC stocks (3 LTE)

Model version	Simulation of lab mineralization data	Simulation of field SOC stocks with field calibration	Simulation of field SOC stocks with lab calibration (specific or mean parameters)
2 pools, fixed k	Slightly lower performances	Underestimation of SOC storage in 2/3 LTE for some EOM	Best performances for 3/3 LTE
2 pools, optimized k 3 pools, fixed k 3 pools, optimized k	Good and equivalent performances	Good and equivalent performances for 3/3 LTE	Overestimation of SOC storage in 3/3 LTE

3.1.4 Conclusion and recommendation for modeling EOM with RothC

We tested different model versions of Roth-C for simulating SOC dynamics after repeated EOM applications. The model performances varied according to the considered LTE and to the calibration approach, and therefore no specific model version stood out from the others as the best for simulating EOM with Roth-C in any scenario. Yet, we suggest using the parameterization based on laboratory incubations for general applicability. In this context, the approach of varying the size and rate constant of two EOM pools seems most suitable. For the four most important groups of EOM, Table 10 provides the numbers of the corresponding parameters.

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

Table 10. Mean (95% CI) of parameters suggested for modeling EOM with RothC. fDEOM and fREOM are the sizes of the respective decomposable and resistant pools of EOM, and kDEOM and kREOM are the corresponding annual decay rate constants.

	fDEOM	fREOM	kDEOM	kREOM
Animal manure	0.37 (0.30 - 0.45)	0.63 (0.55 - 0.70)	11.25 (8.54 - 13.97)	0.16 (0.12 - 0.19)
Compost	0.18 (0.12 - 0.24)	0.82 (0.76 - 0.88)	11.65 (9.82 - 13.48)	0.14 (0.12 - 0.15)
Digestate	0.22 (0.17 - 0.28)	0.78 (0.72 - 0.83)	14.32 (11.53 - 17.11)	0.14 (0.11 - 0.17)
Sludge	0.34 (0.27 - 0.42)	0.66 (0.58 - 0.73)	15.25 (13.42 - 17.08)	0.20 (0.15 - 0.26)

Overall, we proposed a set of EOM parameters for 56 EOM types, based on laboratory mineralization data and adapted to each model version. More tests are needed in the future to investigate the relationship between EOM parameters from lab and field trials, identify the best model version and validate the use of laboratory mineralization data for simulating long-term C storage in the field.

The data above can be used to simulate the long-term effect of EOM addition on SOC stocks, and the model RothC has a long history of studies where EOM addition was investigated in this regard. We do not, however, suggest any EOM emission factor. First of all, the effect of EOM addition on soil depends on the application rate, which makes a universal EF, even for the same type of EOM, meaningless. Rather, we suggest using the improved parameterization for the model RothC to evaluate EOM addition in terms of soil carbon storage. Secondly, the effect of adding EOM on SOC strongly depends on site conditions such as climate, soil properties, and management. This is different to adding biochar as an EOM, as biochar stability is intrinsic and less influenced by site properties as compared to any other organic amendment.

3.2. Effects of pH and liming on SOC decomposition rates

Beyond the stability of the EOM's themselves, their decomposition, as well as decomposition of any organic material in soil, is influenced by various biotic and abiotic factors. In CarboSeq the effect of soil pH and liming on SOC has been evaluated with the goal to decide whether to include pH as a modifying factor into the RothC model.

Soil acidity influences plant growth and microbial activity in soil as well as soil structure. Liming, which is already an established agronomic practice to enhance soil pH, could potentially be a management tool to mediate pH effects on SOC sequestration, but better understanding of resulting net effects are needed, e.g., to allow the integration of pH effects in predictive models of soil carbon sequestration. Soil pH influences the structure, composition and activities of microbial communities, which are driving the transformations of soil organic carbon as well as the fluxes of greenhouse gases (GHG) from arable soils, such as emissions of nitrous oxide (N₂O). Acidic soils with pH < 5.5 cover approximately 30-40% of the world's arable land (Kunhikrishnan et al. 2016) and often result in suboptimal plant growth. Therefore, liming with calcium (Ca²⁺) and magnesium (Mg²⁺) rich materials is a common agricultural practice to raise soil pH and crop yields. Yet, the effect of liming on organic C cycling and SOC sequestration remains controversial. Liming induces increases in plant productivity and may enhance the return of organic C from exudates and residues, potentially increasing SOC stocks. However, liming of acidic soils could also increase soil biological activity, favoring organic matter mineralization and increasing soil CO₂ respiration rates and thus decrease SOC stocks. At the nexus of these processes, the role of soil microorganisms in contributing to long-term stabilization of organic C in soil ecosystems needs to be better understood. Potential pH and liming-mediated changes in microbial communities and carbon use efficiency (CUE) might also play a crucial role on C stabilization. Finally, liming is known to ameliorate soil structure as high Ca²⁺ concentrations may enhance the formation of stable aggregates, which in turn enhance physical SOC protection and decrease mineralization rates.

In Task 3.4 on liming and soil pH, we reviewed empirical information on interactions between soil pH and dynamics of SOC changes in agricultural soils in order to elucidate how SOC decomposition rates and plant inputs are modulated by pH. These parameters determine the net effect of liming on SOC. The information was analyzed in a way to enable possible consideration of soil pH as a driver for SOC in the modeling framework of CarboSeq. Overall, we studied whether there is strong enough evidence for a net effect of soil pH and liming on soil organic carbon stocks to justify an implementation of pH effects into the RothC model.

For the purpose of this task, we relied on two review publications (Wang et al. 2021; Zhang, Liang, et al. 2022) of which the latter was partially funded and carried out within EJP Soil

CarboSeq. Briefly, these studies provide no evidence for a significant and persistent liming effect on SOC stocks of agricultural soils. Wang et al. (2021) reviewed 1570 observations from 121 field-based studies worldwide within their meta-analysis. They reported positive yield effects particularly on acidic soils but concluded that the overall effect of liming on SOC is slightly positive but not significant. There were, however, subgroups in their analysis (e.g., medium acidic soils, soils with low initial SOC content, soils with C/N ratios > 15) that responded positively to liming. The response of SOC stocks to liming varied with various liming and fertilization practices. One main conclusion regarding liming effects on SOC stocks from this study is that eventual higher plant inputs, related to higher productivity, are counterbalanced by the observed significantly higher soil respiration rates, i.e. by higher soil microbial activity. Zhang, Liang, et al. (2022) conducted a meta-analysis using 1474 paired observations from 124 studies to explore the effect of liming on GHG emissions with focus on soil biological factors. In conjunction with the study of Wang et al. (2021), these authors also found significantly higher CO₂ release, which they ascribed to higher respiration rates, both heterotrophic and autotrophic. However, they could not confirm the strong positive yield effect described by Wang et al. (2021). Most important, Zhang, Liang, et al. (2022) report no effect of liming on SOC stocks, suggesting ‘that increased C inputs may compensate for the increased soil respiration, resulting in small or no net differences in terms of SOC after lime application’.

Together, there is no strong and systematic evidence of a net effect of liming on SOC stocks in agricultural soils. Therefore, we did not implement a pH response function into RothC.

4. Assessment of different organic amendments on long-term SOC stocks

Stabilizing organic materials via aerobic or anaerobic decomposition (i.e., composting or fermentation) or pyrolysis to biochar comes at the expense of reducing the carbon bound in the material for eventual conversion to SOM. Previous research has indicated that the long-term retention of organic carbon in the soil was very similar (13% on average) for plant material (feed) directly applied to the soil, or material that underwent different ways of biological processing (was fed to animals and applied as manure, or plant material and manure that underwent anaerobic digestion before being added to the soil). Because the different processes generate EOM of different stability (as also indicated in Table 10), these results point towards a trade-off between off-site stabilization and in-soil mineralization (Thomsen et al. 2013).

Here, we compared different pathways of plant biomass use. We used a version of RothC that has two additional pools. Two EOM pools (DEOM, REOM) were added as described in Mondini et al. (2017) and the implementation of two biochar pools is described in (Keel et al. (2023). Formally, these versions are the same, whereas the partitioning coefficients and decomposition rate constants vary between the materials in accordance with Tables 2 and 10.

First, we demonstrate the effect that different stabilities of EOM amendments have on SOC stocks using RothC. For this purpose, we simulated SOC evolution for a field from a long-term cropland trial in Switzerland (p24A) that received only mineral fertilizer (Maltas et al. 2018). The crop rotation was composed of maize, winter wheat, spring barley, winter rapeseed and spring oat. Between 1976 and 2013 the SOC stocks decreased by 11.4 t ha^{-1} . This is common for long-term experiments in Switzerland (Keel et al. 2019).

For our tests, we assumed that five tons of C in different forms of exogenous organic matter were added per year in addition to plant C inputs.

For compost, digestate and manure, mean parameters given in Table 10 were used. The values given in parenthesis were used to estimate upper and lower confidence intervals of the SOC evolution. For the lower SOC estimates, parameters characterizing EOMs with lower stability were taken (i.e. high fraction of rapidly decomposing pool (fDEOM), low fraction of slowly decomposing pool (fREOM) and high decomposition rates (k values) for both pools). For the higher SOC estimates, parameters characterizing EOMs with higher stability were taken.

For biochar, the parameters shown in the second column of Table 2 were applied. To simulate the SOC evolution for upper and lower confidence intervals, the parameters in the first (upper confidence interval) and last column (low confidence interval) were used.

In the case of plant material, two different values of the RothC parameters describing the quality of plant material added to the soil were used. The default value for the ratio of

decomposable plant material (DPM) vs. resistant plant material (RPM pool) for most agricultural crops and improved grassland is set to 1.44 and means that 59 % of the incoming plant material is easily decomposable and 41 % is more resistant to decomposition. In addition, we ran simulations with a DPM/RPM ratio of 0.67 which is the suggested parameter for unimproved grassland (Coleman and Jenkinson 1996). Mean and confidence intervals of SOC were calculated based on these two simulations.

Fig. 12: Change in soil organic carbon stock assuming five tons of carbon were added annually as different organic amendments.

After about three decades of annual EOM applications, SOC stocks seem to move towards a new steady state in the case of all EOMs except biochar (Fig. 12; Table 11). The latter can be explained by its high stability, with the labile fraction of biochar being on average smaller than 2 % (BC1, Table 2). Changes in SOC for biochar vary slightly for different decades due to changes in crop types grown. Increases in soil organic carbon stocks compared to the baseline were highest after biochar additions, intermediate for digestate, compost and animal manure, and lowest for plant material (Table 12).

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

Table 11. Average year-to-year change in SOC ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) for four different decades (last period is only 8 years long) in response to annual additions of 5 t of different types of organic amendments. With the exception of biochar, decadal changes decline with time, suggesting a new steady-state is reached.

Year	Plant	Manure	Digestate	Compost	Biochar
1977-1986	1.17	1.83	2.33	2.44	4.49
1987-1996	0.35	0.78	1.06	1.10	4.66
1997-2006	0.39	0.52	0.64	0.66	4.75
2007-2014	-0.08	0.01	0.07	0.07	4.46

Table 12: Mean SOC stock changes relative to the baseline in response to annual inputs of five t C ha^{-1} of different EOM.

Organic amendment type	SOC change 1977-2014 (t C ha^{-1})	Annual SOC change ($\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)
Plant	30.8	0.79
Animal manure	43.8	1.12
Compost (average for plant material and manure)	55.1	1.41
Digestate (average for plant material and manure)	53.4	1.37
Biochar	187.3	4.80

Next, we estimated how much C would remain after processing identical amounts of plant biomass. Loss rates of C for different processes were gathered from the literature (Table 13). During rumen digestion in cattle, 70% of C intake is lost (i.e., converted to milk and meat, as well as to CO_2 and CH_4 from metabolism) (Thomsen et al. 2013), i.e. 30% are excreted. During storage of animal manure 13–28% of C is lost as summarized in Wüst-Galley, Keel, and Leifeld

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

(2020). The loss rates were estimated for an average storage duration of 1.5 months (0–3 months) and depended on the type of manure (storage type or from which animal) and the amount of straw added (as bedding material). For our calculations, we used an average value of 21%. For green waste compost, an average C loss of 44.2% was reported in a recent meta-analysis (Ye et al. 2023). Carbon losses of 70-79 % were found for three full-scale anaerobic digestion units with different feedstocks (Schievano et al. 2011). During pyrolysis, 54% of biomass C is lost (assuming a mean biochar yield of 46% as described in chapter 2.4), and pool sizes and rate constants were chosen to match typical composition of European biochars (as provided in Table 2). Final amounts of C remaining as a result of the different processing methods range between 7% (anaerobic digestion of manure) and 100% (plant material directly added to soil, Table 13). For the simulations with RothC, we assumed an initial amount of 10 t C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ of plant material was available. After anaerobic digestion, storage or composting, between 1.6 to 4.6 t C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ remained if only the averages of each process were considered (i.e. plant material/manure were no longer distinguished; Table 14).

Table 13. Amount of carbon remaining after different pathways of exogenous organic matter processing before adding the product to soil. n.a. does not apply.

Organic amendment type	Initial C in plant material (%)	C remaining after cattle feeding (%)	C remaining after storage, composting, anaerobic digestion or pyrolysis (%)	C remaining for application on soil (%)
Plant	100	n.a	n.a	100
Animal manure	100	30 ^a	79 ^b	24
Compost (plant material)	100	n.a.	56 ^c	56
Compost (manure)	100	30 ^a	56 ^c	17
Digestate (plant material)	100	n.a	24 ^d	24
Digestate (manure)	100	30 ^a	24 ^d	7

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

Biochar	100	n.a	46 ^e	46
---------	-----	-----	-----------------	----

^a (Thomsen et al. 2013)

^b (Wüst-Galley, Keel, and Leifeld 2020)

^c (Ye et al. 2023)

^d (Schievano et al. 2011)

^e Mean biochar yield for woody and non-woody feedstock (Table 1)

Table 14: Amounts of C added to the soil for simulations presented in Fig. 13 and resulting average SOC stock changes relative to the baseline.

Organic amendment	C input for simulations (t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)	SOC change after 39 years (t C ha⁻¹)	Annual SOC change (t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)	SOC change relative to added C (%)
Plant	10	61.1	1.57	16
Animal manure	2.4	21.0	0.54	22
Compost (average for plant material and manure)	3.6	39.7	1.02	28
Digestate (average for plant material and manure)	1.6	17.1	0.44	27
Biochar	4.6	172.2	4.42	96

Based on the assumptions we used, transformation of biomass to biochar would clearly lead to highest SOC stocks. Among the other organic amendments, SOC stocks are highest for the addition of unprocessed plant material (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13: Change in soil organic carbon stock assuming ten tons of plant material-C were added per hectare and year or processed (i.e. digested/stored/pyrolyzed) and remaining amounts (see Table 14) were added to the soil.

5. Conclusions

Based on a comprehensive literature review and analysis of published and new data, improved parameters for biochar and other organic amendments are proposed for simulating soil carbon turnover with the RothC model. For EOMs, the parameters are more specific than the generic parameters for FYM in RothC26.3. For biochar, the proposed parameters are based on a thorough analysis of all available decomposition studies and the quality of biochar as used in practice. The literature review also highlighted the effects of abiotic and biotic factors on biochar stability in soil. However, the available information does not justify the inclusion of biochar-specific rate modifiers in the model. Furthermore, the effect of pH and liming on SOC storage was reviewed, showing that they have multiple effects that tend to offset each other..

The newly derived parameters were used to simulate the effect of treating organic residues in different ways typical of current agricultural systems. We conclude that the trade-off between off-site stabilization and in-soil mineralization does not compromise the use of biochar for soil C storage. This means that despite the high C losses of about 50 % during biochar production, higher amounts of C remain in the soil because biochar has very low decomposition rates. In terms of C sequestration efficiency, biochar thus clearly outperforms the other biomass processing pathways. However, additional factors such as nutrient availability of EOMs and environmental effects during processing, storage and soil application such as nutrient leaching or gaseous emissions should be considered when making practical recommendations.

References

- Bruun, S., S. Clauson-Kaas, L. Bobuřská, and I. K. Thomsen. 2014. 'Carbon dioxide emissions from biochar in soil: role of clay, microorganisms and carbonates', *European Journal of Soil Science*, 65: 52-59.
- Budai, Alice, Daniel P. Rasse, Alessandra Lagomarsino, Thomas Z. Lerch, and Lisa Paruch. 2016. 'Biochar persistence, priming and microbial responses to pyrolysis temperature series', *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 52: 749-61.
- Byrd, Richard H., Peihuang Lu, Jorge Nocedal, and Ciyou Zhu. 1995. 'A Limited Memory Algorithm for Bound Constrained Optimization', *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 16: 1190-208.
- Cagnarini, Claudia, Giancarlo Renella, Jochen Mayer, Juliane Hirte, Rainer Schulin, Benjamin Costerousse, Anna Della Marta, Simone Orlandini, and Lorenzo Menichetti. 2019. 'Multi-objective calibration of RothC using measured carbon stocks and auxiliary data of a long-term experiment in Switzerland', *European Journal of Soil Science*, 70: 819-32.
- Chao, L., W. D. Zhang, and S. L. Wang. 2018. 'Understanding the dominant controls on biochar decomposition using boosted regression trees', *European Journal of Soil Science*, 69: 512-20.
- Chen, Haotian, Florent Levavasseur, Denis Montenach, Marc Lollier, Christian Morel, and Sabine Houot. 2022. 'An 18-year field experiment to assess how various types of organic waste used at European regulatory rates sustain crop yields and C, N, P, and K dynamics in a French calcareous soil', *Soil and Tillage Research*, 221: 105415.
- Chen, Xi, Junjie Lin, Peng Wang, Shuai Zhang, Dan Liu, and Biao Zhu. 2022. 'Resistant soil carbon is more vulnerable to priming effect than active soil carbon', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 168: 108619.
- Coleman, K., and D. S. Jenkinson. 1996. 'RothC-26.3 - A Model for the turnover of carbon in soil.' in David S. Powlson, Pete Smith and Jo U. Smith (eds.), *Evaluation of Soil Organic Matter Models: Using Existing Long-Term Datasets* (Springer Berlin Heidelberg: Berlin, Heidelberg).
- Dechow, Rene, Uwe Franko, Thomas Kätterer, and Hartmut Kolbe. 2019. 'Evaluation of the RothC model as a prognostic tool for the prediction of SOC trends in response to management practices on arable land', *Geoderma*, 337: 463-78.
- Doblas-Rodrigo, Álvaro, Patricia Gallejones, Ainara Artetxe, and Pilar Merino. 2023. 'Role of livestock-derived amendments in soil organic carbon stocks in forage crops', *Science of The Total Environment*, 901: 165931.
- EBC. 2012-2022. "European Biochar Certificate - Guidelines for a sustainable production of biochar." In, 63. Arbaz, Switzerland. .
- EU. 2021. '<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021R2088>'. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021R2088>.
- Fang, Yunying, Bhupinder P. Singh, Loïc Nazaries, Alexander Keith, Ehsan Tavakkoli, Neil Wilson, and Balwant Singh. 2019. 'Interactive carbon priming, microbial response and biochar persistence in a Vertisol with varied inputs of biochar and labile organic matter', *European Journal of Soil Science*, 70: 960-74.
- FAO. 2022. "Global soil organic carbon sequestration potential map - SOCseq v1.1. Technical report." In, edited by FAO. Rome.
- Farina, Roberta, Elena Testani, Gabriele Campanelli, Fabrizio Leteo, Rosario Napoli, Stefano Canali, and Fabio Tittarelli. 2018. 'Potential carbon sequestration in a Mediterranean organic vegetable cropping system. A model approach for evaluating the effects of compost and Agro-ecological Service Crops (ASCs)', *Agricultural Systems*, 162: 239-48.
- Gasser, Anton A., Julius Diel, Kerstin Nielsen, Paul Mewes, Christof Engels, and Uwe Franko. 2022. 'A model ensemble approach to determine the humus building efficiency of organic amendments in incubation experiments', *Soil Use and Management*, 38: 179-90.

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

- Gerzabek, M. H., F. Pichlmayer, H. Kirchmann, and G. Haberhauer. 1997. 'The Response of Soil Organic Matter to Manure Amendments in a Long-Term Experiment at Ultuna, Sweden', *European Journal of Soil Science*, 48: 273-82.
- Harvey, O. R., L. J. Kuo, A. R. Zimmerman, P. Louchouart, J. E. Amonette, and B. E. Herbert. 2012. 'An index-based approach to assessing recalcitrance and soil carbon sequestration potential of engineered black carbons (biochars)', *Environ Sci Technol*, 46: 1415-21.
- IBI. 2015. 'International Biochar Initiative. Standardized product definition and product testing guidelines for biochar that is used in soil', *Int. Biochar Initiat*, 23.
- IPCC. 2019. "2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories." In, edited by E. Calvo Buendia, K. Tanabe, A. Kranjc, J. Baasansuren, M. Fukuda, S. Ngarize, A. Osako, Y. Pyrozhenko, P. Shermanau and S. Federici. Switzerland: IPCC National Greenhouse Gas Inventories Programme Technical Support Unit.
- Ithaka-Institute. 2024. "Production quantities and C-sink potential of EBC-certified Biochar in 2023." In, edited by Ithaka-Institute. Zenodo; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10679330>.
- Jha, Pramod, Brij Lal Lakaria, A. K. Vishwakarma, R. H. Wanjari, M. Mohanty, Nishant K. Sinha, J. Somasundaram, G. S. Dheri, A. K. Dwivedi, Raj Paul Sharma, Muneshwar Singh, R. C. Dalal, A. K. Biswas, A. K. Patra, and S. K. Chaudhari. 2021. 'Modeling the organic carbon dynamics in long-term fertilizer experiments of India using the Rothamsted carbon model', *Ecological Modelling*, 450: 109562.
- Jiang, Xinyu, Karolien Deneff, Catherine E. Stewart, and M. Francesca Cotrufo. 2016. 'Controls and dynamics of biochar decomposition and soil microbial abundance, composition, and carbon use efficiency during long-term biochar-amended soil incubations', *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 52: 1-14.
- Kamoni, P. T., P. T. Gicheru, S. M. Wokabi, M. Easter, E. Milne, K. Coleman, P. Falloon, K. Paustian, K. Killian, and F. M. Kihanda. 2007. 'Evaluation of two soil carbon models using two Kenyan long term experimental datasets', *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 122: 95-104.
- Karan, Shivesh Kishore, Dominic Woolf, Elias Sebastian Azzi, Cecilia Sundberg, and Stephen A. Wood. 2023. 'Potential for biochar carbon sequestration from crop residues: A global spatially explicit assessment', *GCB Bioenergy*, 15: 1424-36.
- Karhu, Kristiina, Annemieke I. Gärdenäs, Jaakko Heikkinen, Pekka Vanhala, Mikko Tuomi, and Jari Liski. 2012. 'Impacts of organic amendments on carbon stocks of an agricultural soil — Comparison of model-simulations to measurements', *Geoderma*, 189-190: 606-16.
- Keel, Sonja G., Thomas Anken, Lucie Büchi, Andreas Chervet, Andreas Fliessbach, René Flisch, Olivier Huguenin-Elie, Paul Mäder, Jochen Mayer, Sokrat Sinaj, Wolfgang Sturny, Chloé Wüst-Galley, Urs Zihlmann, and Jens Leifeld. 2019. 'Loss of soil organic carbon in Swiss long-term agricultural experiments over a wide range of management practices', *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 286: 106654.
- Keel, Sonja G., Daniel Bretscher, Jens Leifeld, Albert von Ow, and Chloé Wüst-Galley. 2023. 'Soil carbon sequestration potential bounded by population growth, land availability, food production, and climate change', *Carbon Management*, 14: 2244456.
- Keith, Alexandra, Balwant Singh, and Bhupinder Pal Singh. 2011. 'Interactive Priming of Biochar and Labile Organic Matter Mineralization in a Smectite-Rich Soil', *Environmental Science & Technology*, 45: 9611-18.
- Kunhikrishnan, A., R. Thangarajan, N. S. Bolan, Y. Xu, S. Mandal, D. B. Gleeson, B. Seshadri, M. Zaman, L. Barton, C. Tang, J. Luo, R. Dalal, W. Ding, M. B. Kirkham, and R. Naidu. 2016. 'Chapter One - Functional Relationships of Soil Acidification, Liming, and Greenhouse Gas Flux.' in Donald L. Sparks (ed.), *Advances in Agronomy* (Academic Press).
- Kuzyakov, Y., I. Subbotina, H. Q. Chen, I. Bogomolova, and X. L. Xu. 2009. 'Black carbon decomposition and incorporation into soil microbial biomass estimated by C-14 labeling', *Soil Biology & Biochemistry*, 41: 210-19.

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

- Kuzyakov, Yakov, Irina Bogomolova, and Bruno Glaser. 2014. 'Biochar stability in soil: Decomposition during eight years and transformation as assessed by compound-specific ^{14}C analysis', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 70: 229-36.
- Lehmann, Johannes, Samuel Abiven, Markus Kleber, Gen-Xing Pan, Bhupinder Pal Singh, Saran Sohi, and Andrew Zimmerman. 2015. 'Persistence of biochar in soil', *Biochar for Environmental Management: Science, Technology and Implementation*: 235-82.
- Lehmann, Johannes, and Stephen Joseph. 2015. 'Biochar for environmental management: an introduction.' in, *Biochar for environmental management* (Routledge).
- Leifeld, J., R. Reiser, and H. R. Oberholzer. 2009. 'Consequences of Conventional versus Organic farming on Soil Carbon: Results from a 27-Year Field Experiment', *Agronomy Journal*, 101: 1204-18.
- Levavasseur, Florent, Gwenaëlle Lashermes, Bruno Mary, Thierry Morvan, Bernard Nicolardot, Virginie Parnaudeau, Laurent Thuriès, and Sabine Houot. 2022. 'Quantifying and simulating carbon and nitrogen mineralization from diverse exogenous organic matters', *Soil Use and Management*, 38: 411-25.
- Levavasseur, Florent, Bruno Mary, Bent T. Christensen, Annie Duparque, Fabien Ferchaud, Thomas Kätterer, Hélène Lagrange, Denis Montenach, Camille Resseguier, and Sabine Houot. 2020. 'The simple AMG model accurately simulates organic carbon storage in soils after repeated application of exogenous organic matter', *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*, 117: 215-29.
- Li, Simeng, Scott Harris, Aavudai Anandhi, and Gang Chen. 2019. 'Predicting biochar properties and functions based on feedstock and pyrolysis temperature: A review and data syntheses', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 215: 890-902.
- Lu, Weiwei, Weixin Ding, Junhua Zhang, Huanjun Zhang, Jiafa Luo, and Nanthi Bolan. 2015. 'Nitrogen Amendment Stimulated Decomposition of Maize Straw-Derived Biochar in a Sandy Loam Soil: A Short-Term Study', *PLOS ONE*, 10: e0133131.
- Luo, Y., M. Durenkamp, M. De Nobili, Q. Lin, and P. C. Brookes. 2011. 'Short term soil priming effects and the mineralisation of biochar following its incorporation to soils of different pH', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 43: 2304-14.
- Maltas, Alexandra, Hedi Kebli, Hans Rudolf Oberholzer, Peter Weisskopf, and Sokrat Sinaj. 2018. 'The effects of organic and mineral fertilizers on carbon sequestration, soil properties, and crop yields from a long-term field experiment under a Swiss conventional farming system', *Land Degradation & Development*, 29: 926-38.
- Mao, Li, Sam G. Keenor, Chao Cai, Steve Kilham, Joanne Murfitt, and Brian J. Reid. 2022. 'Recycling paper to recarbonise soil', *Science of The Total Environment*, 847: 157473.
- Mondini, C., M. L. Cayuela, T. Sinicco, F. Fornasier, A. Galvez, and M. A. Sánchez-Monedero. 2017. 'Modification of the RothC model to simulate soil C mineralization of exogenous organic matter', *Biogeosciences*, 14: 3253-74.
- Mondini, C., K. Coleman, and A. P. Whitmore. 2012. 'Spatially explicit modelling of changes in soil organic C in agricultural soils in Italy, 2001–2100: Potential for compost amendment', *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 153: 24-32.
- Nguyen, Binh Thanh, and Johannes Lehmann. 2009. 'Black carbon decomposition under varying water regimes', *Organic Geochemistry*, 40: 846-53.
- Noirot-Cosson, P. E., E. Vaudour, J. M. Gilliot, B. Gabrielle, and S. Houot. 2016. 'Modelling the long-term effect of urban waste compost applications on carbon and nitrogen dynamics in temperate cropland', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 94: 138-53.
- Peltre, Clément, Bent T. Christensen, Sophie Dragon, Christian Icard, Thomas Kätterer, and Sabine Houot. 2012. 'RothC simulation of carbon accumulation in soil after repeated application of widely different organic amendments', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 52: 49-60.

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

- Rodrigues, Leonor, Alice Budai, Lars Elsgaard, Briec Hardy, Sonja G. Keel, Claudio Mondini, César Plaza, and Jens Leifeld. 2023. 'The importance of biochar quality and pyrolysis yield for soil carbon sequestration in practice', *European Journal of Soil Science*, 74: e13396.
- Schievano, Andrea, Giuliana D'Imporzano, Silvia Salati, and Fabrizio Adani. 2011. 'On-field study of anaerobic digestion full-scale plants (Part I): An on-field methodology to determine mass, carbon and nutrients balance', *Bioresource Technology*, 102: 7737-44.
- Schimmelpfennig, Sonja, Claudia Kammann, Jan Mumme, Sven Marhan, Chris Bamminger, Gerald Moser, and Christoph Müller. 2017. 'Degradation of *Miscanthus x giganteus* biochar, hydrochar and feedstock under the influence of disturbance events', *Applied Soil Ecology*, 113: 135-50.
- Smith, Jo, Assefa Abegaz, Robin B. Matthews, Madhu Subedi, Egil R. Orskov, Vianney Tumwesige, and Pete Smith. 2014. 'What is the potential for biogas digesters to improve soil carbon sequestration in Sub-Saharan Africa? Comparison with other uses of organic residues', *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 70: 73-86.
- Speratti, Alicia B., Joan Romanyà, Jordi Garcia-Pausas, and Mark S. Johnson. 2018. 'Determining the Stability of Sugarcane Filtercake Biochar in Soils with Contrasting Levels of Organic Matter', *Agriculture*, 8: 71.
- Thomsen, Ingrid K., Jørgen E. Olesen, Henrik B. Møller, Peter Sørensen, and Bent T. Christensen. 2013. 'Carbon dynamics and retention in soil after anaerobic digestion of dairy cattle feed and faeces', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 58: 82-87.
- Tits, M., A. Elsen, J. Bries, and H. Vandendriessche. 2014. 'Short-term and long-term effects of vegetable, fruit and garden waste compost applications in an arable crop rotation in Flanders', *Plant and Soil*, 376: 43-59.
- Ventura, Maurizio, Giorgio Alberti, Pietro Panzacchi, Gemini Delle Vedove, Franco Miglietta, and Giustino Tonon. 2019. 'Biochar mineralization and priming effect in a poplar short rotation coppice from a 3-year field experiment', *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 55: 67-78.
- Ventura, Maurizio, Giorgio Alberti, Maud Viger, Joseph R. Jenkins, Cyril Girardin, Silvia Baronti, Alessandro Zaldei, Gail Taylor, Cornelia Rumpel, Franco Miglietta, and Giustino Tonon. 2015. 'Biochar mineralization and priming effect on SOM decomposition in two European short rotation coppices', *GCB Bioenergy*, 7: 1150-60.
- Wang, Jinyang, Zhengqin Xiong, and Yakov Kuzyakov. 2016. 'Biochar stability in soil: meta-analysis of decomposition and priming effects', *GCB Bioenergy*, 8: 512-23.
- Wang, Yan, Zhisheng Yao, Yang Zhan, Xunhua Zheng, Minghua Zhou, Guangxuan Yan, Lin Wang, Christian Werner, and Klaus Butterbach-Bahl. 2021. 'Potential benefits of liming to acid soils on climate change mitigation and food security', *Global Change Biology*, 27: 2807-21.
- Woolf, Dominic, and Johannes Lehmann. 2012. 'Modelling the long-term response to positive and negative priming of soil organic carbon by black carbon', *Biogeochemistry*, 111: 83-95.
- Woolf, Dominic, Johannes Lehmann, Stephen Ogle, Ayaka W. Kishimoto-Mo, Brian McConkey, and Jeffrey Baldock. 2021. 'Greenhouse gas inventory model for biochar additions to soil', *Environmental Science & Technology*, 55: 14795-805.
- Wüst-Galley, G., S.G. Keel, and J. Leifeld. 2020. 'A model-based carbon inventory for Switzerland's mineral agricultural soils using RothC.', *Agroscopy Science*, 105: 1-110.
- Yang, Yan, Ke Sun, Lanfang Han, Yalan Chen, Jie Liu, and Baoshan Xing. 2022. 'Biochar stability and impact on soil organic carbon mineralization depend on biochar processing, aging and soil clay content', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 169: 108657.
- Ye, Pingping, Linfa Fang, Dan Song, Muyuan Zhang, Ronghua Li, Mukesh Kumar Awasthi, Zengqiang Zhang, Ran Xiao, and Xinping Chen. 2023. 'Insights into carbon loss reduction during aerobic composting of organic solid waste: A meta-analysis and comprehensive literature review', *Science of The Total Environment*, 862: 160787.

Final report work package 3 – Biochar and other organic amendments

- Zhang, Hui-Min, Zhi Liang, Yong Li, Zhao-Xiong Chen, Jin-Bo Zhang, Zu-Cong Cai, Lars Elsgaard, Yi Cheng, Kees Jan van Groenigen, and Diego Abalos. 2022. 'Liming modifies greenhouse gas fluxes from soils: A meta-analysis of biological drivers', *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 340: 108182.
- Zhang, Yeye, Yuteng Dang, Jinxia Wang, Qiu Huang, Xiukang Wang, Liru Yao, Nangia Vinay, Kailiang Yu, Xiaoxia Wen, Youcai Xiong, Yuncheng Liao, Juan Han, and Fei Mo. 2022. 'A synthesis of soil organic carbon mineralization in response to biochar amendment', *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 175: 108851.
- Zimmerman, Andrew R. 2010. 'Abiotic and microbial oxidation of laboratory-produced black carbon (biochar)', *Environmental Science & Technology*, 44: 1295-301.